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Research Article

**EFFICACY OF TOPICAL TACROLIMUS IN TREATMENT OF
ORAL LICHEN PLANUS****Atheer Thamer Alsaedi¹, Rawan Majed Allehaybi¹, Manar Matar Alslymi¹,
Faris Thamer Alsaedi¹, Manal Abdullah Almehmadi¹, Dalya Hussien Ali Alali²**¹Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah,²Alfarabi Colleges, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia**Abstract:****Introduction:**

Corticosteroids were the treatment of option for symptomatic oral lichen planus. However, to avoid the associated adverse effects of corticosteroids, many non-steroidal medications were developed with unclear efficacy. Tacrolimus is one of these medications that was recommended by the results of the primary studies. This review aimed to evaluate the evidence of using tacrolimus as an alternative to steroid in treatment of OLP.

Methods: An electronic search in MDLINE was achieved to identify randomized controlled trials aimed to assess the clinical efficacy of tacrolimus in treatment of histologically confirmed OLP. After screening of the eligible studies, studies which met the inclusion criteria subjected to data extraction into tables to summary the findings of the included studies.

Results: The electronic search resulted in 21 studies, from them only 8 studies found eligible. Among included studies, the sample size ranged from 27 participants to 68 participants and the mean age ranged from 32±10.5 years old to 67.8±11 years old. About the efficacy of tacrolimus, the majority of studies reported higher efficacy than the comparison placebo, topical steroids, or other non-steroidal medications. Four included studies reported efficacy of tacrolimus which was comparable to triamcinolone acetonide [24], steroid [23], oral dapsone [23], retinoid [23], or pimecrolimus.

Conclusions: topical tacrolimus is efficient alternative of corticosteroids in the treatment of OLP. It showed a higher or comparable efficacy to all comparison drugs and no study reported significant lower efficacy of tacrolimus.

Keywords: Lichen planus, Oral, Symptomatic, Therapy, Corticosteroids,

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral lichen planus is (OLP) a T-cell mediated inflammatory condition with unknown etiology, which involves oral mucosal membrane in intermittent periods of activation and remission with low potential of malignant transformation [1]. The prevalence of OLP among adults is estimated to range between 0.5 to 2% mainly among 30-60 years old adults with higher tendency towards females [2,3]. However, OLS can also affect children with many cases developed the OLP after hepatitis B vaccination [4]. Diagnosis of OLP is based on clinical and histological features, however the clinical presentation may be adequate in classical bilateral reticular form of the disease [5]. Predisposing factors of OLP include genetic factors, stress, anxiety, depression, dental trauma, hypersensitivity reaction, diabetes mellitus, thyroid dysfunction and systematic medications [5].

Management of OLP depends on the type of lesion, while reticular lesions only need clinical observation, the erosive and ulcerative lesions require treatment of symptoms and reduction of chance of malignant transformation [6]. Studies reported that treatment of OLP with topical corticosteroids achieved different success rate ranged from 30% to 100% of treated patients [7,8]. Systematic corticosteroids showed effective reduction of lichen planus lesions, particularly when other organs such as skin and genitalia are affected [9].

New therapy modalities have been developed to treat refractory lesions including laser therapy, biologics, curcuminoids and newly emerged phototherapy [10,11]. Primary clinical trials conducted on non-steroidal agents such as dapsone, tacrolimus or retinoid showed comparable results to these of steroidal counterparts with less side effects. Since these medications have been newly introduced, evidence regarding their use is still inconclusive. This review aimed to evaluate the evidence supporting use of non-steroidal agents in treatment of OLP.

METHODS:

An electronic search in MDLINE was achieved by the authors in December 2018 using search terms such as "oral lichen planus" AND (treatment OR management OR intervention) AND (tacrolimus) AND (efficacy OR effectiveness OR success OR improvement). The inclusion criteria were randomized controlled trials aimed to assess the clinical efficacy of tacrolimus in treatment of OLP, thus cases series was excluded [12-15]. Studies should confirm the diagnosis of OLP histologically and any lichenoid lesions should be excluded.

Additionally, a study assessed only histological outcomes without evaluation of clinical response of treatment was excluded from this review [16]. After screening of the eligible studies, studies which met the inclusion criteria subjected to data extraction into tables to summary the findings of the included studies. These findings were discussed in a narrative review to explore the efficacy of tacrolimus on treatment of OLP.

RESULTS:

The electronic search resulted in 21 studies, from them only 8 studies found eligible as demonstrated in table 1. The full texts of 8 studies were read and they met the criteria of inclusion in the review [17-24]. The sample size ranged from 27 participants in a study of Siponen *et al.* [24] to 68 participants in a study conducted by Hettiarachchi *et al.* [22]. The mean age of included patients ranged from 32±10.5 years old [23] to 67.8±11 years old [20].

Regarding intervention, all included studies used topical 0.1% ointment of tacrolimus, the non-steroidal treatment of OLP. Among included studies, the efficacy of tacrolimus was compared to other non-steroidal, steroidal medications or placebo. The comparison was made with topical triamcinolone acetonide in three included studies [17,23,24], with clobetasol propionate in three included studies [18,19,22], with pimecrolimus in two studies [20,21], with retinoid in study of Singh *et al.* [23], or with placebo in study conducted by Siponen *et al.* [24]. The duration of treatment ranged from 3 weeks as in studies of Singh *et al.*[23] and Hettiarachchi *et al.* [22] to duration of 12 weeks [19] when the primary outcomes were assessed, however some studies continue to follow up the patients for extra 3 or 6 months [17,20,24]. The most common method used to assess the outcomes of treatment was an ordinal score of lesion size and shape adopted in five included studies [17,18,20,22,24]. Other included studies assessed the pain either alone or in combination with lesion characteristics by visual analog scale [18,20,22,24].

About the efficacy of tacrolimus, the majority of studies reported higher efficacy than the comparison placebo [24], topical steroids [18,19,22], or other non-steroidal medications [17]. Four included studies reported efficacy of tacrolimus which was comparable to triamcinolone acetonide [24], steroid [23], oral dapsone [23], retinoid [23], or pimecrolimus [20,21]. However, no study showed lower efficacy of tacrolimus than other comparison drugs.

DISCUSSION:

Although many treatment modalities have been developed to manage OLP, no intervention seems to be curative. Oral lichen planus is mostly asymptomatic, however symptomatic lesions, especially erosive lesions, can be very annoying for the patients. They significantly reduce the patients' quality of life and requires prompt intervention [25]. As lichen planus is an immunological mediated disease, corticosteroids are the first option therapy. Patients suffer many side effects after using of corticosteroids [5], thus studies assessed the effectiveness of non-steroidal medications with aim to treat oral lichen planus in hope of being more tolerable than steroidal treatment. This review aimed to accumulate the evidence assessing the efficacy of non-steroidal medication called tacrolimus. Siponen *et al.* found a significant higher efficacy of tacrolimus than that in placebo, which is a good starting point. Furthermore, in comparison to a steroidal drug (clobetasol), tacrolimus showed a higher efficacy regardless of sample size and statistical power of the study [18,19,22]. In addition, this superior efficacy is consistent whatever the method used to assess the clinical response of the treatment. In a study of Hettiarachchi *et al.*, [22] visual analogue scale used to assess the post-treatment pain and TC was used to assess the response of lesion, while in other studies a net clinical score [19] or modified ordinal scales [18] were used to assess the clinical response. Despite all

included studies recruited small sample size, some of these studies divided the sample on many groups which may result in loss of statistical power.

Tacrolimus was compared to other non-steroidal drug triamcinolone acetonide in a study of Laeijendecker *et al.* [17], where a higher significant efficacy was found, while in a study of Siponen *et al.* [24] no significant difference was reported. The non-significant difference may be attributed to the dividing of 27 patients on 3 groups which compromised the power of the study to detect significant differences. Similar justification may be applied to the non-significant difference between tacrolimus efficacy and each of oral dapsone and topical retinoid. Differently, the non-significant difference between efficacy of tacrolimus and pimecrolimus seemed to be less affected by sample size [20,21].

CONCLUSION:

Based on the findings of this review, we concluded that topical tacrolimus is efficient alternative of corticosteroids in the treatment of OLP. It showed a higher or comparable efficacy to all comparison drugs and no study reported significant lower efficacy of tacrolimus. Further studies with large sample size are required to establish the application of tacrolimus on clinical practice and to assess the tolerability of the patients.

Table (1): The findings of the included study regarding the efficacy of TAC on treatment of OLP

Study	Sample size	Patient age mean (SD)	Intervention	Comparison (if any)	Duration of treatment	Method of outcome assessment	Conclusion
(Siponen <i>et al.</i> , 2017) [24]	27	TAC group = 60 (9), TRI group = 51 (12), Placebo group = 58 (10)	TAC 0.1% ointment (n=11)	Topical steroid of 0.1% TRI paste (n=7) or placebo (n=9)	An initial trial period of 6-9 weeks and a follow-up period of 6 months.	A VAS with clinical score (CS, range 0-130) was developed to measure the clinical signs and symptoms	TAC and TRI were significantly more effective than placebo in reducing the CS at week 3. No difference in the efficacy was noted between TAC and TRI

(Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2017) [23]	40	32 (10.5)	TAC (n=10)	Oral dapsone (n=10), or topical retinoid (n=10). Topical steroids such as topical TRI (n=10)	3 months	Comparison of pre- and post-treatment symptoms and signs scores (0-4) according to Raj <i>et al.</i> [26]	No significant differences between groups
(Hettiara chchi <i>et al.</i> , 2017) [22]	68	Total = 46.7 (12.6) TAC group= 46.7 (13.2) and Clobetasol group = 46.9 (12.1)	TAC 0.1% cream	Clobetasol propionate 0.05% cream	3 weeks	Assessment of pain using VAS (from 0-10). Assessment of clinical response using score (0-5) according to TC	The results suggest that tacrolimus 0.1% cream is more effective alternative to topical steroid and can be considered a first-line therapy in OLP.
(Vohra <i>et al.</i> , 2016) [21]	40	Total = 35.7 (13.5), TAC group=39.8 (14.6), and pimecroli mus= 31.7 (11.2)	TAC 0.1% ointment (n=20)	Pimecroli mus 1% cream (n=20)	8 weeks	Net clinical score (NCS) that modified of the semiquantitative scale for the monitoring of OLP severity proposed by Piboonniyom <i>et al.</i> [27]	Pimecroli mus 1% cream seems to be as effective as tacrolimus 0.1% ointment
(Arduino <i>et al.</i> , 2014) [20]	30	Total =67.8, TAC group= 66.4 (11.1), Pimecroli mus group= 69.1 (10.7)	TAC 0.1% ointment mixed with an equivalent amount of 4% hydroxyethyl cellulose gel.	Pimecroli mus 1% cream mixed with an equivalent amount of 4% hydroxyethyl cellulose gel.	8 weeks followed by 6 months follow up	The clinical lesions were scored according to the criteria scale used by Thongprasom <i>et al.</i> [28] the pain was assessed by VAS score (0-10)	Both drugs were effective at inducing clinical improvement, with no statistical difference.

(Sonthali and Singal, 2012) [19]	40	Total = 34.7 (14.6), TAC group = 35 (13.2), Clobetasol group = 34.4 (16.2)	TAC 0.1% ointment (n=20)	Topical clobetasol propionate 0.05% ointment (n=20)	8-12 weeks	The primary outcome measure was defined as the percentage of patients attaining required response scored by NCS	TAC showed better effectiveness. The percentages of patients reporting "good" or "very good" treatment responses at week 8 were 74% in the clobetasol group and 100% in the tacrolimus group
(Corrocher et al., 2008) [18]	32	43.6 (18.4)	TAC 0.1% ointment (n=16)	Clobetasol 0.05% ointment (n=16)	6 weeks	The lesion size assessed use score from absent to severe (0-3) and pain assessed using score (0-3) from absent to severe	Tacrolimus 0.1% ointment is more effective than clobetasol propionate 0.05% ointment in the treatment of OLP
(Laeijndecker et al., 2006) [17]	40	Total =58, TAC group = 57, and TRI group= 58.	TAC 0.1% ointment (n=20)	TRI 0.1% ointment (n=20)	6 weeks then treatment was discontinued earlier when patients showed a complete healing. The follow-up period was 3 months.	Ordinal score recorded as worse, unchanged, improved or healed. The ordinal (ranked) scoring involved assessing the severity and the extent of the disease.	The treatment with topical tacrolimus 0.1% ointment four times daily induced a better initial therapeutic response than triamcinolone acetonide 0.1% ointment in patients with symptomatic OLP.

Tiamcinolone acetonide (TRI), Tacrolimus (TAC), Visual Analog Scale (VAS), Thongprasom Classification (TC)

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